

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR STUDYING COMMUNICATIVE AND CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

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ANNOTATION. The article talks about the role and importance of scientific methods in the formation of the communicative and creative potential of future technology teachers; sincerity, fluency and communication skills are the main link in the organization of the educational process.

Key words: communicative and creative potential, scientific methods, communicative competence, pedagogical skills, innovative technologies, expert.

INTRODUCTION

In the UN Conventions on Education, Science and Culture “On Technical and Vocational Education” and “On Combating Discrimination in Education”, “Ma”. In the Agreement “on the import of materials of cultural, scientific and cultural content”, much attention was paid to the issues of improving the status of teachers on a global scale, developing the communicative competence of teachers based on international qualification requirements. In the world, the creation of broad conditions for the quality of training of teachers and students of higher educational institutions, the exchange of experience and the development of their communicative competence, and the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process are of particular importance.

MAIN PART

Professional growth and development of a person as a specialist manifests itself in the form of a process in its essence. Professional maturity is a process of important periods of professional maturity, the development of a person’s ideas, starting from adolescence and the end of professional activity until retirement age. The formation and development of a creative personality depends on the mutual compatibility of changes in his internal and external world, socio-economic conditions, and the content of activities that require continuity and continuity from birth to the end of his life. Mastering the skills of professional creative activity is not only the integration of practical skills and qualifications, mastering methods and means of effectively organizing the activities of a specialist, but also knowledge of the methodology of professional creativity, the development of creative thinking and creative activity. it is necessary to master a sufficient level of personal qualities of a creative nature.

Despite the fact that in recent years significant research and practical work has been carried out on the formation of creative qualities of students, most teachers still do not know how to effectively form creative qualities in individuals (in themselves and in students). ...they don't understand it. In order to achieve high efficiency in the work of educational institutions, education system management bodies annually develop educational programs and create new textbooks. This helps both students and teachers grow professionally.

Creativity is considered a missing factor in educational activities; in order to fully understand the general essence of the process of formation and development of a person's creative qualities, it is necessary first of all to understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". For example, according to Ken Robinson, "Creativity is a collection of original ideas that have value." And Gardner, in his research, explains this concept: "Creativity is a practical action performed by a person, which must reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value." In Ambale's view, creativity means "possessing highly unusual skills along with deep knowledge of a particular field." Many teachers believe that they do not have the ability to be creative. This can be justified on two different grounds: first, most teachers fail to adequately explain what the concept of "creativity" actually means; secondly, they do not know what qualities are directly reflected in the basis of creativity. It is worth noting here that every person by nature has the ability to be creative. So how can teachers demonstrate their creativity? Here's Patti Drapeau's advice: "If you don't consider yourself a creative person, I suggest you start organizing creative thinking classes now. It's not really about whether you are creative or creative, but about how you organize your activities in a creative way and try to try out new ideas in practice. Comprehensive thinking in activities organized in a creative spirit requires students to rely on many ideas when solving educational problems, problems and problems. In contrast, one-way thinking is based on only one correct idea. In observation, it is impossible to deny the one-sidedness and versatility of thinking on this issue. When completing a task or solving a problem, the student looks for several possible solutions (multidimensional thinking), and then settles on the only correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result.

Based on the above ideas, the concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows: A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings and certain types of activities. Creativity characterizes a person as a whole or his specific activity. characteristics. A number of researchers have studied the fact that today's educational practice cannot acquire a creative character, and the reasons for this and the conditions for their elimination can be explained as follows: in many cases, teachers become acquainted only with the content of the subject, but the thinking process is of great importance, they do not provide any information. about how attention and requests can develop. The lack of clear instructions from the teacher, the effectiveness of the approach to the lesson, and the use of methods and strategies by students aimed at improving their learning activities are at a low level. However, in order to give clear and understandable instructions on the development of students' thinking skills, the teacher must control the students' learning activities, introducing students to ways of thinking (critical, creative), ways to effectively develop skills and guide it.

Today, it is possible to achieve the formation of creative qualities in students based on the following important approaches: a clear definition of educational tasks, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students, the socio-psychological uniqueness of the team; be able to reasonably choose effective forms, methods and means of organizing the educational process; be able to determine the results of students studying the material based on the requirements of the curriculum, level of education and development of students; carry out various types of work to develop the interest, needs and activity of students in learning; carrying out various educational activities in circles, clubs or societies in class and outside of class; the use of various training weapons, modern technical means, information and advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process; It is necessary to carry

out systematic tasks such as self-analysis, self-evaluation and correction of shortcomings in personal performance.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, technology has greater potential for developing a teacher's humanistic communicative competence than normative subjects in terms of content and pedagogy. In all the topics considered, the leading position is occupied by personality-oriented, humanitarian aspects of interaction between the teacher and students.

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